

Case Study

Management of Chronic Foot Eczema Through Ayurvedic Shodhana Therapy: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Eczema is a chronic inflammatory dermatosis with recurrent exacerbations and significant impact on quality of life. In Ayurveda, a comparable condition is described as Vicharchika, a subtype of Kushta. Virechana (therapeutic purgation) is considered a principal Shodhana therapy for skin disorders. Case presentation: A 40-year-old male construction worker presented with chronic eczematous lesions over both feet associated with severe pruritus, burning sensation, and persistent serous discharge for four years. Despite the chronicity of symptoms, routine investigations were within normal limits. The patient was managed exclusively with Ayurvedic interventions, primarily classical Virechana therapy following appropriate preparatory procedures, along with local wound care and internal medications. Outcome: Significant reduction in inflammation, discharge, and itching was observed within weeks. Complete healing of lesions with minimal residual hyperpigmentation was achieved within one month. No recurrence was noted during one year of follow-up. Conclusion: This CARE guideline-compliant case report highlights the potential role of Ayurvedic Shodhana therapy, particularly Virechana, in achieving sustained remission in chronic eczema (Vicharchika).

INTRODUCTION

Eczema is a chronic relapsing inflammatory skin disorder characterized by pruritus, erythema, scaling, and oozing lesions. The disease results from a complex interplay of genetic predisposition, epidermal barrier dysfunction, and

immune dysregulation. Persistent itching and visible skin lesions often contribute to psychological stress and impaired quality of life.

Genetic studies have demonstrated an association between filaggrin gene defects and increased susceptibility to eczema and other atopic

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conditions. In Ayurvedic literature, eczema is described under *Vicharchika*, a form of *Kushta*, involving vitiation of *Kapha* and *Pitta doshas* along with *Rakta dhatu*. Ayurvedic management emphasizes correction of internal imbalance through systemic purification and lifestyle modification. This report presents a CARE-compliant documentation of a chronic case of eczema successfully managed through Ayurvedic purificatory measures.

PATIENT INFORMATION

A 40-year-old male, working as a building construction laborer, presented with complaints of recurrent itchy rashes over both feet for four years. He also reported a chronic, non-healing wound with serous discharge over the posterior aspect of the lateral malleolus and dorsum of the left foot for three years. There was no history of diabetes mellitus, hypertension, or other systemic illness. No significant family history was reported.

CLINICAL FINDINGS

On examination, dry scaly plaques were observed over the dorsum of the right foot. The left foot revealed a 4 × 3 cm serous-discharging lesion over the posterior lateral malleolus and dorsum, with mild edema, tenderness, increased local temperature, foul odor, and surrounding induration. Intense pruritus and burning sensation were noted.

DIAGNOSTIC ASSESSMENT

Routine hematological investigations including hemoglobin, total and differential leukocyte counts, erythrocyte sedimentation rate, and urine analysis were within normal limits. Culture and sensitivity testing of wound discharge showed no microbial growth. Based on clinical features, the condition was diagnosed as chronic eczema,

corresponding to *Vicharchika* in Ayurveda. Occupational exposure to cement was considered a precipitating factor, suggesting exogenous eczema.

THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTION

The treatment plan focused on *Shodhana* therapy with classical *Virechana*, preceded by *Purva karma* procedures. Initially, *Deepana–Pachana* medicines were administered to enhance digestive fire and facilitate *Ama pachana*. This was followed by *Snehapana* with medicated ghee for an appropriate duration based on patient tolerance.

Subsequently, *Sarvanga Abhyanga* (whole-body oil massage) and *Bashpa Swedana* (steam sudation) were performed for three days to mobilize vitiated *Doshas* toward the gastrointestinal tract. *Virechana* was then administered, resulting in sixteen bouts of purgation, considered moderate and adequate.

Post-procedure dietary regulation (*Samsarjana krama*) was followed for three days. Local wound care included daily cleansing with *Panchavalka Kwatha Prakshalana*. Supportive oral medications included *Arogyavardhini Vati* (one tablet thrice daily for one month) and *Panchatiktaka Guggulu Ghrita* (10 ml twice daily before food for one month).

FOLLOW-UP AND OUTCOMES

Noticeable improvement in inflammatory signs was observed within five days of treatment. Pruritus, burning sensation, and discharge gradually subsided. Complete healing of lesions occurred within one month, leaving mild hyperpigmentation. The patient was advised to use protective footwear and avoid direct exposure to cement. During a follow-up period of one year, no recurrence was reported.

Figure 1: BEFORE TREATMENT -

Figure 2: AFTER TREATMENT -

DISCUSSION

Eczema is characterized by an impaired skin barrier, leading to increased transepidermal water loss and heightened immune reactivity. From an Ayurvedic standpoint, *Vicharchika* arises due to *Agnimandya*, accumulation of *Ama*, and vitiation of *Kapha* and *Pitta doshas*. *Virechana* is the treatment of choice for eliminating vitiated *Pitta* and purifying *Rakta dhatu*.

In this case, *Deepana–Pachana* corrected metabolic dysfunction, while *Snehapana*, *Abhyanga*, and *Swedana* facilitated mobilization of morbid *Doshas*. Therapeutic purgation effectively interrupted disease pathogenesis. Local application of *Panchavalkala Kwatha* supported wound cleansing and healing. Incorporation of counseling, yoga, and *Pranayama* addressed the

psychological stress associated with chronic eczema.

PATIENT PERSPECTIVE

The patient reported significant relief from itching and discomfort, improved sleep, and enhanced confidence in daily activities following treatment.

INFORMED CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying clinical images.

CONCLUSION

This CARE-compliant case report demonstrates that Ayurvedic *Shodhana* therapy, particularly *Virechana*, can offer effective and sustained management of chronic eczema (*Vicharchika*).

Systemic purification combined with lifestyle modification may help achieve long-term remission and improved quality of life.

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